

Appendix F - Search strategies to establish microbiological cut-off values for antimicrobial resistance

Bacteria

Set	String
#1 Microbial species	"Bifidobacterium adolescentis" OR "Bifidobacterium animalis" OR "Bifidobacterium bifidum" OR "Bifidobacterium breve" OR "Bifidobacterium thermophilum" OR "Bifidobacterium pseudolongum" OR "Bifidobacterium pseudocatenulatum" OR "Bifidobacterium catenulatum" OR "B. adolescentis" OR "B. animalis" OR "B. bifidum" OR "B. breve" OR "B. thermophilum" OR "B. pseudolongum" OR "B. pseudocatenulatum" OR "B. catenulatum" OR "Brevibacterium lactofermentum" OR "Corynebacterium glutamicum" OR "Corynebacterium jeikeium" OR "Corynebacterium pseudodiphtheriticum" OR "Corynebacterium minutissimum" OR "Corynebacterium striatum" OR "Corynebacterium urealyticum" OR "Corynebacterium xerosis" OR "Corynebacterium amycolatum" OR "Corynebacterium auris" OR "Corynebacterium glucuronolyticum" OR "Corynebacterium argenteratense" OR "B. lactofermentum" OR "C. glutamicum" OR "C. jeikeium" OR "C. pseudodiphtheriticum" OR "C. minutissimum" OR "C. striatum" OR "C. urealyticum" OR "C. xerosis" OR "C. amycolatum" OR "C. auris" OR "C. glucuronolyticum" OR "C. argenteratense" OR "Lactobacillus acidophilus" OR "Lactobacillus crispatus" OR "Lactobacillus gallinarum" OR "Lactobacillus gasseri" OR "Lactobacillus johnsonii" OR "Lactobacillus amylovorus" OR "L. acidophilus" OR "L. crispatus" OR "L. gallinarum" OR "L. gasseri" OR "L. johnsonii" OR "L. amylovorus" OR "Lactobacillus plantarum" OR "Lactobacillus farciminis" OR "Lactobacillus paraplanctarum" OR "Lactobacillus pentosus" OR "L. plantarum" OR "L. farciminis" OR "L. paraplanctarum" OR "L. pentosus" OR "Lactiplantibacillus plantarum" OR "Companilactobacillus farciminis" OR "Lactiplantibacillus paraplanctarum" OR "Lactiplantibacillus pentosus" OR "C. farciminis" OR "Lactobacillus rhamnosus" OR "L. rhamnosus" OR "Lactocaseibacillus rhamnosus" OR "Lactobacillus casei rhamnosus" OR "Lactobacillus reuteri" OR "Lactobacillus mucosae" OR "L. reuteri" OR "L. mucosae" OR "Limosilactobacillus reuteri" OR "Lactobacillus fermentum subsp. reuteri" OR "Limosilactobacillus mucosae" OR "Lactobacillus casei" OR "Lactobacillus paracasei" OR "L. casei" OR "L. paracasei" OR "Lactocaseibacillus casei" OR "Lactocaseibacillus paracasei" OR "Lactobacillus delbrueckii" OR "Lactobacillus helveticus" OR "Lactobacillus delbrueckii subsp. Bulgaricus" OR "L. delbrueckii" OR "L. helveticus" OR "L. delbrueckii subsp. Bulgaricus" OR "Lactobacillus bulgaricus" OR "L. bulgaricus" OR "Lactobacillus brevis" OR "Lactobacillus buchneri" OR "Lactobacillus fermentum" OR "Lactobacillus kerifi" OR "Lactobacillus kefir" OR "Lactobacillus parabuchneri" OR "Lactobacillus sanfranciscensis" OR "Lactobacillus sanfrancisco" OR "L. brevis" OR "L. buchneri" OR "L. fermentum" OR "L. kerifi" OR "L. kefir" OR "L. parabuchneri" OR "L. sanfranciscensis" OR "L. sanfrancisco" OR "Levilactobacillus brevis" OR "Lentilactobacillus buchneri" OR "Limosilactobacillus fermentum" OR "Lentilactobacillus kerifi" OR "Lentilactobacillus parabuchneri" OR "Fructilactobacillus sanfranciscensis" OR "F. sanfranciscensis" OR "Lactobacillus curvatus" OR "Lactobacillus sakei" OR "Lactobacillus alimentarius" OR "Lactobacillus salivarius" OR "Lactobacillus ruminis" OR "Lactobacillus animalis" OR "L. curvatus" OR "L. sakei" OR "L. alimentarius" OR "L. salivarius" OR "L. ruminis" OR "L. animalis" OR "Latilactobacillus curvatus" OR "Latilactobacillus sakei" OR "Companilactobacillus alimentarius" OR "Ligilactobacillus salivarius" OR "Ligilactobacillus ruminis" OR "Ligilactobacillus animalis" OR "C. alimentarius" OR "Lactococcus lactis" OR "L. lactis" OR "Leuconostoc mesenteroides" OR "Leuconostoc lactis" OR "Leuconostoc pseudomesenteroides" OR "Leuconostoc citreum" OR "Leuconostoc carnosum" OR "L. mesenteroides" OR "L. lactis" OR "L. pseudomesenteroides" OR "L. citreum" OR "L. carnosum" OR "Pediococcus pentosaceus" OR "Pediococcus dextrinicus" OR "Pediococcus acidilactici" OR "Pediococcus parvulus" OR "P.

	<p>pentosaceus" OR "P. dextrinicus" OR "P. acidilactici" OR "P. parvulus" OR "Lapidilactobacillus dextrinicus" OR "L dextrinicus" OR "Propionibacterium acidipropionici" OR "Propionibacterium freudenreichii" OR "Propionibacterium acnes" OR "P. acidipropionici" OR "P. freudenreichii" OR "P. acnes" OR "Cutibacterium acnes" OR "C. acnes" OR "Acidipropionibacterium acidipropionici" OR "A. acidipropionici" OR "Streptococcus thermophilus" OR "S. thermophilus" OR "Streptococcus salivarius subsp. thermophilus" OR "Actinomadura roseorufa" OR "Actinomadura yumaensis" OR "A. roseorufa" OR "A. yumaensis" OR "Corynebacterium casei" OR "Corynebacterium stationis" OR "C. casei" OR "C. stationis" OR "Enterococcus faecium" OR "Enterococcus mundtii" OR "E. faecium" OR "E. mundtii" OR "Eubacterium" OR "Bacillus amyloliquefaciens" OR "Bacillus coagulans" OR "Bacillus clausii" OR "Bacillus atrophaeus" OR "Bacillus flexus" OR "Bacillus fusiformis" OR "Bacillus licheniformis" OR "Bacillus lentus" OR "Bacillus mojavensis" OR "Bacillus megaterium" OR "Bacillus vallismortis" OR "Bacillus smithii" OR "Bacillus subtilis" OR "Bacillus pumilus" OR "Geobacillus stearothermophilus" OR "Lysinibacillus fusiformis" OR "B. amyloliquefaciens" OR "B. coagulans" OR "B. clausii" OR "B. atrophaeus" OR "B. flexus" OR "B. fusiformis" OR "B. licheniformis" OR "B. lentus" OR "B. mojavensis" OR "B. megaterium" OR "B. vallismortis" OR "B. smithii" OR "B. subtilis" OR "B. pumilus" OR "G. stearothermophilus" OR "L. fusiformis" OR "Bacillus paralicheniformis" OR "Bacillus velezensis" OR "Bacillus sonorensis" OR "Bacillus brevis" OR "Bacillus cereus" OR "Bacillus firmus" OR "Bacillus toyonensis" OR "B. paralicheniformis" OR "B. velezensis" OR "B. sonorensis" OR "B. brevis" OR "B. cereus" OR "B. firmus" OR "B. toyonensis" OR "Weizmannia coagulans" OR "W. coagulans" OR "Shouchella clausii" OR "Alkalihalobacillus clausii" OR "S. clausii" OR "A. clausii" OR "Priestia flexa" OR "P. flexa" OR "Lysinibacillus fusiformis" OR "L. fusiformis" OR "Lederbergia lenta" OR "L. lenta" OR "Priestia megaterium" OR "P. megaterium" OR "Bacillus stearothermophilus" OR "B. stearothermophilus" OR "Brevibacillus brevis" OR "Cytobacillus firmus" OR "C. firmus" OR "Streptomyces albus" OR "Streptomyces aureofaciens" OR "Streptomyces azureus" OR "Streptomyces cinnamomensis" OR "Streptomyces lasaliensis" OR "S. albus" OR "S. aureofaciens" OR "S. azureus" OR "S. cinnamomensis" OR "S. lasaliensis" OR "Kitasatospora aureofaciens" OR "K. aureofaciens" OR "Streptomyces virginiae" OR "S. virginiae" OR "Streptomyces lasalocidi" OR "S. lasalocidi" OR "Actinoplanes utahensis" OR "A. utahensis" OR "Clostridium butyricum" OR "C. butyricum" OR "Paenibacillus lentus" OR "P. lentus" OR "Gluconobacter oxydans" OR "Xanthomonas maltophilia" OR "Stenotrophomonas maltophilia" OR "Enterobacter cloacae" OR "Enterobacter spp." OR "Alcaligenes acidovorans" OR "Ensifer adhaerens" OR "Ensifer fredii" OR "Escherichia coli" OR "Gluconobacter frateurii" OR "Ketogulonicigenium vulgare" OR "Methylococcus capsulatus" OR "Paracoccus carotinifaciens" OR "Pseudomonas fluorescens" OR "Rhodopseudomonas palustris" OR "Serratia rubidaea" OR "Sphingomonas elodea" OR "G. oxydans" OR "X. maltophilia" OR "S. maltophilia" OR "E. cloacae" OR "A. acidovorans" OR "E. adhaerens" OR "E. fredii" OR "E. coli" OR "G. frateurii" OR "K. vulgare" OR "M. capsulatus" OR "P. carotinifaciens" OR "P. fluorescens" OR "R. palustris" OR "S. rubidaea" OR "S. elodea" OR "Alcaligenes odorans" OR "Alcaligenes faecalis subsp. faecalis" OR "Sinorhizobium adhaerens" OR "Sinorhizobium fredii" OR "Ketogulonicigenium vulgare" OR "A. odorans" OR "A. faecalis subsp. faecalis" OR "S. adhaerens" OR "S. fredii" OR "K. vulgare"</p>
<p>#2 Antibiotics and resistance</p>	<p>(antibiotic* OR antimicrobial* OR "anti-biotic*" OR "anti-microbial*" OR drug* OR gentamicin OR kanamycin OR streptomycin OR vancomycin OR erythromycin OR telithromycin OR tylosin OR ampicillin OR fosfomicin OR colistin OR ciprofloxacin OR chloramphenicol OR thiamphenicol OR clindamycin OR tetracycline) NEAR/7 (resistan* OR susceptib*)</p>
<p>#3 Final results</p>	<p>#1 AND #2 AND PY=(2013-2022) AND LA=(English)</p>

Fungi

Set	String
#1 Microbial species	"Komagataella pastoris" OR "K. pastoris" OR "Pichia pastoris" OR "Zygosaccharomyces pastoris" OR "P. pastoris" OR "Z. pastoris" OR "Komagataella phaffi" OR "K. phaffi" OR "Ogataea angusta" OR "O. angusta" OR "Pichia angusta" OR "Hansenula angusta" OR "P. angusta" OR "H. angusta" OR "Saccharomyces cerevisiae" OR "S. cerevisiae" OR "Saccharomyces pombe" OR "S. pombe" OR "Schizosaccharomyces pombe" OR "Trichosporon mycotoxinovorans" OR "T. mycotoxinovorans" OR "Apiotrichum mycotoxinivorans" OR "A. mycotoxinivorans" OR "Xanthophyllomyces dendrorhous" OR "X. dendrorhous" OR "Phaffia rhodozyma" OR "P. rhodozyma" OR "Cryptococcus rhodozymus" OR "C. rhodozymus"
#2 Antimycotics and resistance	(antimicrobial* OR antifungal* OR antimycotic* OR "anti-microbial*" OR "anti-fungal*" OR "anti-mycotic*" OR Polyenes OR "amphotericin B" OR nystatin OR Flucytosine OR "5-fluorocytosine" OR Azoles OR Ketoconazole OR Fluconazole OR Itraconazole OR Voriconazole OR Posaconazole OR Isavuconazole OR Echinocandins) NEAR/7 (resistan* OR susceptib*)
#3 Final results	#1 AND #2 AND PY=(2003-2022) AND LA=(English)

#: number; LA: Language; PY: Publication Year.